

HOW DO DIFFERENCES AMONG LEARNERS AFFECT LEARNING PROCESS

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Annotation: *The current article will provide sufficient amount of information regarding to dissimilarities among learners as well as how it can affect to the learning process .*

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Learners vary in their ability to grasp, remember and comprehend the data or information which may show a radical change in the process of learning. Except from ability dissimilarities can be found in individual's age, learning style, background knowledge, character and personal trait.

Every individual differs from each other as well as their brain capacity to process information. Some learn at a low speed, while others comprehend any piece of information swiftly. Some claim that they are visual learners, whereas others include themselves to the group of audio and kinetic learners. If I speak from my own experience, from the observations that I have done it is evident that what type of learner you are is considered to be salient, namely, a fast learner and a slow learner. To give you an idea, preparing for my assignments takes me around 3 hours, while my sister takes about 1 hour as she is a fast learner. Despite a short amount of time she prepares more effectively than me. Moreover, with less stress. The process of learning is not found much exhausting for fast learners as they can pick up new knowledge in a short period of time. These were the most obvious dissimilarities that I noticed over the past 14 years. It always seemed as if I am as a slow learner could not match with the pace that was likely to be 10 or 15 steps ahead of me. Slow learners feel the inferiority of knowledge and pressure of being left behind compared to their peers which might as well be the cause of social issues and not having the courage to express their ideas.

But what causes slowing down the process of learning?

As researches showed one of the main causes of slowing down the brain's capability to learn is overthinking. Professors from the Department of Bioengineering who are Danielle Bassett, Eduardo D.Glandt led a study in relation to this topic. It showed that the ones who take longer to comprehend have no cognitive control which led to the overthinking, triggering unnecessary data and activities.

Taking more time than the other learners shows an exceeding effect on the learning process. The ones who are fast learners capable of acquiring the knowledge relatively faster than those who are considered to be slow learners, resulting the formers pick up more information compared to their peers.

Being the fast or slow learner is not the only variance among learners. Researches has suggested that the individual`s age, aptitude, memory, learning style, personality, motivation and attitude can also affect learning process. As Hassan Ait Bouzid stated „ Age where a learner starts learning a second language impacts on the ultimate achievement of the learner in that second language. Age affects abilities, propensities, attitudes and learning strategies and view. It affects access to the language acquisition device which is restricted by the critical period hypothesis research has demonstrated that puberty is the age-related point beyond which it becomes difficult if not impossible to reach native-like proficiency in second language”.

Even so, is it the same case when it comes to picking up the knowledge that is not related to language learning

Uzbek proverb says that the knowledge which is learned in youth is a curved pattern on stone. Mankind unconsciously gains most of the knowledge, which they will use during their whole lifespan, in a period of being toddler or younger respectively. A brain of the child also works variously compared to adults. Adults might lead a learning process in an effective and practical way, nevertheless results vary. It is sufficient for young learners to make minimum effort in order to memorize the data, whereas adult learners should give their maximum in this case. Even in the sphere of sport, dance or others it is common to start it in a young age if you expect yourself to achieve professionalism in this field. Dozen of studies have proved that 15 months old child have the capability to learn specific cause-effect relationships from statistical data. Also, another major difference between adult and young learners is their behaviour. Adult learners, being relatively more independent, organized and adequate have an advantage to planning the process, even instructing themselves. As we all know motivation plays a huge role in studying. Those who are motivated know why they are doing It, because often it is their own decision and aim. It is proven that adults are more motivated which makes the learning process easier as they learn voluntarily.

It may seem the least consequential trait of yours, even so with knowing what kind of learner you are as well as knowing your learning style, you are potentially improving yourself in aspects of learning. It commences with knowing and recognizing yourself, knowing which method or style is effective for you. You can identify yourself as one of the following learners: visual, auditory, reading and writing and kinesthetic. Prior to identifying your learning style and knowing what type of learner you are you may have been struggling using techniques and strategies that are unsuitable for you. After recognizing one`s dominant learning style an individual becomes more self-confident and self-assured, learns how to use his/her brain best in any situation, also studies productively.

How personality trait can influence in learning process?

One's personality trait may be the main factors of lessening or advancing impact on learning process, effecting in its outcome as well as behaving oneself while attending education places. Traits can cause both negative and positive effects in the process of learning. Individual's determination, dedication and efforts are also related to one own personality traits. Similarly, being skeptical about one's own abilities and giving up in a half way of your path or even worse, before even starting is also personality traits of human-being. Whether being hyper-active or on the contrary, super passive are none other than characteristics. Those traits contribute less or more profits in your journey of learning similar to doing actual effort. One should take into account that even being an intellectual or unintelligent are traits. Even so, to change them in a way that you potentially see yourself or want to be is in your hands.

No matter how, learners differentiate steeply in their interests, ability, gender, learning styles they all are striving to know more about the knowlege of this world with the same goal. Those dissimilarities can not be border in our way if we truly desire to achieve our aim!

References:

1. telfcourse.net
2. <http://www.researchgate.net>
3. Kuzgun, y., & Deryakulu, d. (Eds.). (2004).
4. Individual differences in education.
5. Buss, D. M., & Greiling, H. (1999).
6. Adaptive individual differences.
7. Maltby, J., Day L., & Macaskill, A (2007).
8. Personality, individual differences and intelligence. London: Pearson Education